

Improving performance of air quality monitoring: a qualitative data analysis

Danny Manongga¹, Untung Rahardja², Irwan Sembiring¹, Qurotul Aini³,
Po Abas Sunarya⁴

¹Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Information Technology, Satya Wacana Christian University, Salatiga, Indonesia

²Department of Engineering, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Technology Malaysia, Johor, Malaysia

³Department of Digital Business, Faculty of Economy and Business, University of Raharja, Tangerang, Indonesia

⁴Department of Retail Management, Faculty of Economy and Business, University of Raharja, Tangerang, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Jan 8, 2024

Revised Apr 23, 2024

Accepted Jun 1, 2024

Keywords:

Air quality monitoring

Artificial intelligence

Leximancer 5.0

Qualitative data analysis

Smart environment

ABSTRACT

This research aims to improve performance of air quality monitoring and understand the latest relevant technological developments. Employing the Kitchenham systematic literature review (SLR) method, the study examines 436 journal articles and conference proceedings published from 2019 to 2023, sourced from the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases. The analysis was carried out using Leximancer 5.0 and identified research five themes; i) air quality, ii) artificial intelligence (AI), iii) pollution, iv) middleware, and v) smart environment. The results showed that only 48 journals had strict inclusion and exclusion criteria include relevance to the research theme, methodological quality, and contribution to the research field. In addition, this research integrates AI and middleware, which has significantly contributed to improving air quality. These findings can become the basis for the development of air quality monitoring technology that is more sophisticated and responsive to environmental needs. This research contributes to further understanding air quality monitoring technology trends and designing solutions to improve overall air quality.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Qurotul Aini

Department of Digital Business, Faculty of Economy and Business, University of Raharja

Tangerang, Indonesia

Email: aini@raharja.info

1. INTRODUCTION

Air quality monitoring has long been of primary importance in environmental health and public policy [1], [2]. In the era before the emergence of advanced technology, air quality monitoring and analysis approaches relied heavily on manual methods [3]. Initially, monitoring was carried out through direct observation and periodic collection of air samples, which were then analyzed in the laboratory to determine the concentration of various pollutants [4]. These classical methods are often limited in sampling frequency, which impacts the ability to understand and respond quickly to changes in air quality [5], [6]. At that time, fixed air quality monitoring stations, although providing accurate data, were only able to measure air conditions at specific locations. This creates difficulties in obtaining a comprehensive picture of the regional or global distribution of air pollutants [7], [8]. Additionally, the analytical tools available at that time often required complex and time-consuming procedures, limiting the ability of researchers and policymakers to make rapid, data-driven decisions [9]. This research challenge addresses the severe impacts caused by air pollution on a large scale, including complex phenomena such as smog and industrial air pollution. In this context, particular emphasis is needed on developing technology that can provide a rapid response and

effective in responding to increasingly pressing air quality problems [10], [11]. The approach tends to be reactive rather than proactive, emphasizing mitigating impacts after an air pollution event occurs. Standards and guidelines from international organizations such as the World Health Organization (WHO) are a reference in measuring and controlling air pollution, especially in large cities, which is a significant concern because its negative impacts are limited to human health and environmental and economic stability [12], [13].

This traditional monitoring is also often limited in integrating air quality data with other variables, such as methodology and demographics, which are now crucial in understanding air quality dynamics and their impacts [14], [15]. As technology has developed and there has been a deeper understanding of the importance of air quality, monitoring methods and tools have evolved significantly [16]. The transition to an era of advanced technologies in air quality monitoring, such as internet of things (IoT) sensors, extensive data analysis, and machine learning algorithms, has opened new opportunities for more efficient, accurate and comprehensive monitoring [17]. In addition, this research will explore how transitioning from traditional methods to approaches based on advanced technology has changed how we monitor, analyze and respond to air quality issues. A key focus is understanding how technological advances can be further used to overcome existing challenges in monitoring air quality and protecting public health and the environment [18].

There is a gap in previous research investigating the use of technology in air quality monitoring. However, while these research findings have explored the effectiveness of current technologies, they have not explicitly addressed the integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and middleware in air quality monitoring [19]. Therefore, there is a gap in understanding of the extent to which such advanced technologies can improve monitoring and response to air pollution. Although previous findings have examined the technologies and methods used in air quality monitoring, they may not have specifically explored the qualitative aspects of the data collected. This includes how the data is used, understood, and interpreted by different stakeholders such as researchers, policy makers, and the general public. Therefore, there is a gap in the literature in depth in qualitative analysis of air quality monitoring data to improve monitoring system performance. This research shows that evaluating the effectiveness of current technologies in identifying and responding to air pollution events is important for better air quality management in the future. In comparison with other studies, this study emphasizes the role of more sensitive sensors and sophisticated data processing in improving responses to air pollution. In addition, it also highlights the need to take environmental and social factors into account in the evaluation of technology effectiveness, which can impact the sustainability of implemented solutions. The research design, as presented in Figure 1, was developed using specific three components: research problem (RP), research question (RQ), and research objectives (RO).

RESEARCH COMPONENT	DESCRIPTION	
Research Problem (RP)	RP1	How conventional air quality monitoring methods, which are often limited in geographic coverage and frequency, impact our ability to understand and respond to air quality dynamics in a timely manner.
	RP2	The degree of negative impact of air pollutants on human health and the environment, especially in dense urban areas.
	RP3	Challenges in responding quickly and effectively to large-scale air pollution events, such as smog and industrial disasters.
Research Question (RQ)	RQ1	How can the latest technologies, such as IoT sensors, big data analysis and AI, improve the air quality monitoring and analysis process.
	RQ2	How can technology be used to predict air pollution events and facilitate more effective prevention measures.
	RQ3	How can integration of data from various sources help in a more comprehensive understanding of air quality and its impact on human health and the environment.
Research Objectives (RO)	RQ1	Developing technology-based solutions that can increase the accuracy, coverage and speed of air quality monitoring.
	RQ2	Provides in-depth analysis of how air pollutants affect human health and the environment, with the aim of informing policy and mitigation strategies.
	RQ3	Formulate recommendations for action strategies to overcome air quality problems.

Figure 1. Research design

RP focuses on the challenges faced by traditional air quality monitoring methods. These methods, are often limited in geographic reach and need more data integration difficulties, impacting their effectiveness in responding to changes in air quality and large-scale air pollution events such as smog and industrial pollution. Then, identify the need to overcome approaches that tend to be reactive rather than proactive in dealing with air quality problems, including identifying primary pollutant sources. The RQ revolve around how using advanced technologies, such as IoT sensors, big data analytics, and machine learning, can improve air quality monitoring and analysis. How these technologies can help faster and more effectively respond to large-scale air pollution incidents and how they influence our approach to understanding and managing air quality in urban environments. RO develops a more profound understanding through systematic literature review (SLR) of how advanced technology can be used to improve air quality monitoring. The aims research to value the effectiveness of current technologies in identifying and responding to air pollution events and develop data-based policy recommendations for better air quality management in the future. The SLR approach seeks to identify knowledge gaps, build strong understanding, and formulate effective and efficient strategies for researchers, policymakers and practitioners facing the challenges of urbanization and globalization. This approach is expected to provide new insights and innovative solutions for handling air quality problems in the current era of advanced technology.

The focus on SLR aims to identify knowledge gaps, build solid understanding, and formulate recommendations for future research. Thus, the SLR approach is expected to provide a solid foundation for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to plan, implement and understand air quality research more effectively and efficiently in facing the complex challenges large cities face in the era of globalization and continued urbanization. Beyond a conventional literature review, this research adopts a qualitative data analysis approach, delving into the intricate details of the selected publications. It seeks to discern not only the relevance and methodological quality of the existing research but also the contributions these studies make to the overarching field of air quality monitoring. As a distinctive feature, this study integrates qualitative data analysis with a focus on the identified research themes, emphasizing the role of AI and middleware in the improvement of air quality monitoring.

Underpinning this research is the comprehensive support for advancing air quality monitoring systems, encompassing environmental science, data analysis, and cutting-edge technology. At the heart of these advances is the integration of advanced technologies such as AI and middleware, which are poised to revolutionize the accuracy and responsiveness of air quality monitoring systems. This research underlines the importance of a qualitative analytical approach, which complements insight into air quality; it involves systematically identifying air quality problems and establishing questions and related objectives that guide structured exploration of the topic. A systematic research design is critical to this endeavour, as it outlines clear protocols for data collection, analysis, and interpretation, allowing for actionable insights to be derived. The integration of these technologies holds the promise of significant advancements, contributing to the development of more sophisticated and responsive monitoring systems. By merging a qualitative analytical approach with the latest technological insights, this research aims to provide a nuanced understanding of air quality monitoring trends. The research design systematically presents the identified problems, corresponding questions, and the set objectives, creating a structured foundation for comprehensively exploring air quality-related issues. This research is an initial step that has the potential to lead to innovative solutions to the complex challenges faced by large cities around the world in an era of rapid urbanization and industrialization [20].

The paper is structured as follows: section 2 details the criteria for database selection and the process of defining search keywords. Section 3 presents the research findings, offering a summary of insights, statistical information, and results from qualitative data analysis using Leximancer 5.0. The section also reviews any encountered limitations, ensuring transparency and context to the research. Section 4 concludes the paper by synthesizing findings, discussing implications, and suggesting future research directions.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research methods

Research used Kitchenham SLR method [21], a systematic approach that is relevant and comprehensive. The methodology shown in Figure 2, created by Alzami *et al.* [22], consists of three phases of literature reflection that can assist in planning, conducting, and reporting research [22]. This research combines a qualitative data analysis approach using Leximancer 5.0 tools with the aim of explaining insights in existing literature, contributing to a deeper understanding of the factors that influence air quality monitoring performance.

Figure 2. SLR protocol development

The first phase, “planning the review” emphasizes the importance of planning, starting with planning the review to gain a general understanding of the air quality domain. Then, a review protocol was developed to outline the literature selection process and criteria [23]. Air quality-specific RO and questions were determined, followed by the formulation of a review protocol that included inclusion and exclusion criteria [24]. Research keywords related to air quality were determined, and appropriate research databases were selected for the literature search. The second phase, “conducting the review”, concerns the execution of the review itself. A set of query strings is generated from predefined keywords, and papers are searched against relevant databases [25]. All review processes are conducted according to established protocols, ensuring consistency and accuracy. Data was then extracted from papers that met the criteria for further analysis. The third phase, “reporting the review”, focuses on presenting the results. Each paper is grouped by topic to facilitate analysis. The results of the review, including main findings and conclusions, are then documented. Overall, the Kitchenham method provides a systematic framework and structure.

2.1. Search string and database selection

In attempting to perform automated searches in the air quality domain, this research was faced with the major challenge of identifying relevant studies. These challenges arise due to the breadth of literature available and the variety used by researchers. This strategy was to ensure the inclusion of as many relevant papers as possible, this study decided to adopt a more general approach using search strings. This approach aims to cover a wider spectrum of relevant literature in search results. The strategy used involved applying RQ and a gradual strategy to obtain appropriate search terms.

- Identify key concepts related to air quality, such as monitoring, analysis, management, pollution impacts, and the use of AI.
- Develop a search string using a combination of keywords related to the main concepts that have been identified, as well as adapting to variations and synonyms of terms used in the literature.
- Validate search strings to ensure coverage of important aspects of the research domain and refine based on feedback from other researchers or related domain experts.

The flow diagram in Figure 3, shown in the figure illustrates a careful and structured methodological approach in academic research. First, it determines the identification of the research topic, which is a critical step in determining the focus and scope of the research. With an explicit topic in mind, the researcher then selects the most appropriate database to search for relevant literature, ensuring that the topic is explored comprehensively and from multiple perspectives by choosing the trusted and extensive databases, web of science (WoS) and Scopus, both of which are known for their wealth of scientific literature.

Identify the WoS and Scopus databases as the main sources for collecting articles related to air quality. This study integrates both databases to ensure a comprehensive literature review covering a broad spectrum. The various digital libraries available are: i) WoS [clarivate.com]; ii) IEEEExplore [ieeexplore.ieee.org]; iii) Emerald [emerald.com]; iv) SpringerLink [springerlink.com]; and v) Elsevier [elsevier.com]. The search string, (“improving performance” OR enhancement OR optimization) AND (“air quality monitoring” OR “air quality”) AND (“qualitative data analysis” OR qualitative research OR qualitative study) AND (“artificial intelligence” OR AI) AND (“pollution” OR pollutants OR contaminant)

AND (“middleware”) AND (“smart environment” OR “smart cities”). This search string was designed to search for articles that discuss improving air quality monitoring performance with qualitative data analysis and focus on the use of AI in the context of air quality monitoring, pollution, middleware technology, and smart environments. Through applying this detailed search strategy, it is hoped that the study will be able to identify and include as many relevant papers as possible for further analysis of the factors influencing air quality monitoring performance.

Figure 3. Research database selection

2.2. Review of selected article

Table 1 presents, the sample selection process which is divided based on two main criteria, namely inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria ensure the relevance of the sample to the RQ and objectives, thereby significantly increasing the potential for research results to be applied in the context in question. On the other hand, exclusion criteria play a role in reducing bias by eliminating subjects who may have factors or conditions that could influence the research results. This stage is crucial in filtering out papers that do not fit the research focus or do not meet the specific criteria set for this review.

Table 1. Review protocol

No	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
1	Research related to air quality monitoring	Research not related to monitoring or improving air quality
2	Qualitative data relevant to air quality monitoring	Qualitative data that is not relevant to air quality monitoring
3	Research with strategies or proposed improvements for air quality monitoring	Study without contributions or new solutions for air quality monitoring

The approach described involves a series of detailed steps in the process of selecting relevant literature for a review of air quality. The initial broad and inclusive approach was designed to broaden the scope of the search and collect as many relevant literature sources as possible, with the aim of minimizing the risk of bias that might arise from overly restrictive search parameters. Inclusion criteria were then created to form the basis of a comprehensive literature review, which included studies of air quality modeling performance with a variety of methodologies and outcomes. Although research presented in various formats such as conferences and journals was considered, priority was given to current and complete versions to maintain data integrity. On the other hand, exclusion criteria act as a quality control mechanism by eliminating studies that do not have strong validation methods, thereby ensuring the credibility of the review. A refined screening process was carried out after the initial search to reduce order-induced bias, where the title and abstract of each study were carefully checked to ensure compliance with the research topic and review criteria. Studies that did not meet the initial criteria were then filtered out before full text assessment was carried out. This curated selection approach is key to building a focused and comprehensive literature review, thereby providing a valuable contribution to the understanding of air quality.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Result of selected articles

The literature review process outlined in Table 2, transitioning from an initial pool of 436 articles, is a testament to the rigor and depth demanded in academic research, particularly in the fields of air quality and

intelligent environmental monitoring. This process unfolds in several nuanced and carefully executed stages, ensuring that each selected article significantly contributes to the understanding and advancement of the topic. Table 3 presents, the extensive database search across multiple platforms, including the WoS and Scopus. These databases are known for their comprehensive coverage and include publications from leading publishers like IEEE, Emerald, Springer, and Elsevier. The aim at this stage is to cast a wide net, capturing a broad spectrum of academic discourse that touches upon various facets of air quality. This extensive search yields a considerable volume of potential articles, amounting to 436 papers. This large number reflects the breadth of the topic and the diverse range of research being conducted in this field.

Table 2. Summarizing selected papers

Database initiation	Initiation	Title and abstract selection	Full paper selection
WoS	59	14	6
IEEE	96	27	13
Emerald	47	19	4
Springer	172	36	14
Elsevier	62	32	11
Total	436	127	48

Table 3. Overviews of literature on air quality

Author	Years	Method	Country
Jiang <i>et al.</i> [26]	2023	Deliberative dan choice experiment	China
Fu <i>et al.</i> [27]	2023	Weather Research and Forecasting	China
Kuang and Lin [28]	2023	Differences-in-differences (DID)	China
Wang <i>et al.</i> [29]	2023	Global random forest regression model	Australia
Zhang <i>et al.</i> [30]	2023	Urban development intensity-UDI	China
O'Regan and Nyhan [31]	2023	Narrative meta-review	Ireland
Arbilla <i>et al.</i> [32]	2023	Air sample collection	Brazil
Hama <i>et al.</i> [33]	2023	Perceived air quality (PAQ)	China
Storey <i>et al.</i> [34]	2023	Self-organizing maps (SOM)	Australia
Kuiper <i>et al.</i> [35]	2023	Inverse treatment probability weights	USA
Li <i>et al.</i> [36]	2023	Emission process model	China
Munir <i>et al.</i> [37]	2023	Smart traffic interventions	United Kingdom
Pang <i>et al.</i> [38]	2023	Message-oriented middleware (MOM)	China
Yang <i>et al.</i> [39]	2023	Difference-in-difference (DID)	China
Jiang <i>et al.</i> [40]	2022	Fleet electrification	China
Cao <i>et al.</i> [41]	2022	Difference-in-differences strategy	China
Mangut <i>et al.</i> [42]	2022	Bluetooth low energy (BLE)	China
Majdi <i>et al.</i> [43]	2022	Proposed algorithm	China
Li <i>et al.</i> [44]	2022	Two-way fixed effects model)	China
Pei <i>et al.</i> [45]	2023	Perceived air quality (PAQ)	China
Meena <i>et al.</i> [46]	2022	Data collection	India
Helm <i>et al.</i> [47]	2022	Car scrappage scheme	Germany
Choi <i>et al.</i> [48]	2022	Natural experiment spatial difference	South Korea
Wang <i>et al.</i> [49]	2022	Regression discontinuity design (RDD)	China
Rao <i>et al.</i> [50]	2022	Geographically weighted regression (GWR)	China
Horn and Dasgupta [51]	2022	Remote procedure call (RPC)	USA
Mahmud <i>et al.</i> [52]	2022	Welch's one-way ANOVA	Bangladesh
Gamboa <i>et al.</i> [53]	2022	Proposed algorithm	Brazil
Wang <i>et al.</i> [54]	2022	Convolutional neural network	China
Elbaz <i>et al.</i> [55]	2022	Residual network (ResNet)	China
Liu <i>et al.</i> [56]	2022	Model dubin spasial (SDM)	China
Pathak <i>et al.</i> [57]	2022	Spatial and temporal data analysis	India
Rios <i>et al.</i> [58]	2022	Data collection	Mexico
Zivelonghi and Giuseppi [59]	2022	AulaSicura platform	Italy
Pourkiaei and Romain [60]	2022	Literary analysis	Belgium
Beloconi and Vounatsou [61]	2022	Bayesian geostatistical regression models	Switzerland
Lee and Aghamohammadi [18]	2022	Cross-sectional	Malaysia
Tariq <i>et al.</i> [62]	2022	Aerosol optical depth (AOD)	Pakistan
Xie <i>et al.</i> [63]	2022	Urban surface transport index (USTI)	China
Wan <i>et al.</i> [64]	2022	Weather Research and Forecasting	China
Liu <i>et al.</i> [65]	2022	Model spatial durbin	China
Mehmood <i>et al.</i> [66]	2022	Multi-pollutant profiling	India
Mehmood <i>et al.</i> [66]	2022	Bibliometric	China
Rowley and Karakuş [67]	2022	Long short-term memory (LSTM)	United Kingdom
Yogeswaran <i>et al.</i> [68]	2022	Settle plate	Malaysia
Cobbold <i>et al.</i> [69]	2022	Data survey	Australia

The next phase involves a critical evaluation of the titles and abstracts of these 436 papers. This title and abstract screening serves as the first layer of screening. It is during this stage that the articles are assessed for their direct relevance to the core aspects of the research topic. Keywords, thematic alignment, and preliminary alignment with the RO are crucial factors in this evaluation. The screening process is both selective and exhaustive, ensuring that each article's title and abstract align closely with the research's central themes. As a result, many papers that do not meet the specific preliminary criteria are excluded, significantly reducing the pool to 127 articles. This considerable reduction is indicative of the stringent criteria applied, ensuring that only articles with the most direct relevance and potential contribution to the RO proceed to the next stage.

The full paper selection stage is where the depth and precision of the review process truly come to the forefront. Each of the 127 articles that passed the initial screening is subjected to a comprehensive full-text review. This stage is meticulous and demands a high level of critical analysis. Researchers at this point evaluate the methodological robustness, the rigor of the findings, and the overall contribution of each study to the field. Predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria play a pivotal role here. These criteria, while not explicitly detailed, are crucial in maintaining the integrity and relevance of the review. They likely encompass the methodological soundness of the studies, the contextual significance of the findings, the reputation and impact factor of the journals in which these studies are published, and citation metrics, which serve as indicators of the influence and recognition of the research within the academic community. This thorough evaluation is also mindful of avoiding biases, such as the order effect, where the sequence of paper review might inadvertently influence selection. The process is rigorous and objective, ensuring that each paper is evaluated on its merits. After this in-depth analysis, only 48 of the 436 articles meet the stringent standards set for inclusion. This final selection represents a collection of relevant, high-quality research with a series of carefully structured filters and this process not only ensures selection of the most relevant and high-quality articles, but also reflects rigorous academic research standards and contributes significantly to the understanding of air quality and intelligent environmental monitoring.

The results a comprehensive compilation of studies that collectively offer a deep and diverse understanding of the current state of air quality research, highlighting the breadth of the research field and the specific advances and insights that have been achieved in recent years. The findings show that several studies on air quality use middleware or AI as part of the research methodology. The use of message-oriented middleware (MOM), remote procedure call (RPC), convolutional neural network (CNN), and long short-term memory (LSTM) is seen in several studies. The application of middleware and AI reflects the diversity of technologies used to improve the performance and effectiveness of air quality analysis. Additionally, the findings show that using MOM, RPC, and deep learning algorithms such as CNN and LSTM reflects research efforts to leverage advanced technologies to overcome the complexity of air quality data and gain deep insights.

3.2. Description statistic

The diagram presented in Figure 4, provides a visual representation of the distribution of 48 literature articles related to a specific topic based on year of publication and country of origin between 2019 and 2023. In 2023, China showed many publications reflecting the country's particular urgency or priority concerning air quality issues. Although China stands out in the graph, other countries also show growth in their publications, although less intensively than China [70], [71]. This shows that air quality problems are not only limited to one area but are also a focus in various parts of the world. Overall, the diagram offers an in-depth look at air quality related publications' geographic and temporal distribution. Meanwhile, other countries such as Italy, Switzerland, Belgium, Arabia, Ireland, USA, South Korea, Bangladesh, Mexico, and Pakistan, each with one article recorded, reflect a stable condition in their research output. Furthermore, Brazil, Malaysia, and Australia, which each produced two articles, showed a moderate upward trend in scientific publications, which may indicate that there has been an expansion of research activities or perhaps a growing awareness and need to understand and address air quality problems in these countries. On the other hand, countries such as Spain, the UK, Germany and India, with three articles, show more intensive and consistent research, reflecting a more structured research strategy or a stronger commitment to broader and more diverse environmental issues. In addition, research shows that countries such as Italy, Switzerland, Belgium, Arabia, Ireland, the United States, South Korea, Bangladesh, Mexico, and Pakistan only have one article, which reflects the consistency of their research output. This indicates a phenomenon where there is a limitation in the number of published studies from these countries regarding air quality problems.

This research explores the impact of air pollution in several countries with a comprehensive approach involving systematic analysis. Through collecting and integrating data from various sources, including air sensor data, public health surveys, and environmental predictive models, this research was able to identify complex air pollution patterns and their impacts on human health and the environment. However, further and in-depth studies may be needed to confirm the validity of these findings. Advanced analyzes that

look at larger geographies and demographics could provide more detailed insight into the health risks associated with air pollution in different populations. To overcome these limitations and their potential impact on the results, this study comprehensively explores the topic by considering various aspects. However, to ensure the validity of the findings and the accuracy of the analysis, further and more in-depth research may be needed. This is especially important in identifying concrete solutions related to air quality problems, as well as in understanding their full impact. Overall, the information presented provides a valuable perspective on how interest and focus in air quality research have developed and transformed over the observed period. This diagram also helps identify and highlight that more focused interventions and more profound research may be required to address various air quality-related challenges currently facing or emerging in the future, thereby helping policymakers, researchers, and petitioners.

Figure 4. Number of publications per year and country

3.3. Leximancer results

The analysis carried out using Leximancer 5.0 aims to provide in-depth and comprehensive insight into the main themes, patterns and trends that exist in the literature related to air quality. The results of this analysis will be a strong basis for researchers in formulating conclusions, recommendations and implications for future research, as well as for policy making and practical implementation in the fields of environment and public health. Thus, the use of Leximancer 5.0 in the context of this research is key in gaining a deep and sustainable understanding of important aspects related to air quality.

In qualitative research, data analysis is often categorized into three distinct but interconnected methods: conceptual analysis, relational approach, and temporal analysis. This method systematically categorizes and quantifies specific words or phrases to understand their significance and frequency in the study context. Relational analysis, on the other hand, delves deeper by exploring the relationships and connections between these identified concepts. It seeks to uncover patterns that reveal how different themes are interrelated, often shedding light on cause-and-effect dynamics within the data. Finally, temporal analysis adds the dimension of time, focusing on how concepts, themes, or relationships evolve or are influenced over time. This approach is crucial in understanding trends, changes, and the timing of events, providing insights into how historical contexts or chronological factors impact the subject of study. Together, these three methods offer a comprehensive framework for analyzing qualitative data, each contributing a unique perspective that enriches the overall understanding of the research findings.

3.3.1. Conceptual analysis

Conceptual analysis of the concept map in Figure 5, highlights five main themes: air quality, AI, middleware, pollution, and smart environment. Through the Leximancer analysis technique, where color interpretation is used to provide conceptual meaning to each theme, there are color gradations from red which indicates urgency, to purple which may appear less frequently but is still relevant. In this analysis, the links between these themes become clear. AI and middleware play an important role in optimizing systems to

exploration and integration of these themes to develop comprehensive air quality management and improvement strategies.

The Leximancer 5.0 concept map resulting from qualitative data analysis in the study offers in-depth insight into the interrelationships between various factors that influence air quality [72]. The central theme of “air quality” includes concepts such as “PM” and “CO”, indicating the primary focus of this research is assessing and improving the way we monitor pollutants in the atmosphere. In a technological context, the emergence of “AI” and “models” substantially indicates that there is great potential in the use of machine learning algorithms to predict and analyze air quality patterns, which can help in making data-based decisions to address pollution problems [73]. Additionally, the “middleware” that emerged in the analysis underscores the critical role of technological infrastructure in managing and processing data collected from air quality sensors. This proves the importance of systematic integration between monitoring hardware and data analysis software. Factors such as “energy” and “temperature” are recognized as variables that influence air quality, both indoors and in the external environment, emphasizing the importance of monitoring conditions that influence pollutant levels [74]. The concepts of “work”, “system”, and “building” provide further context for how air quality monitoring is integrated into various aspects of life and infrastructure. “Traffic” and “city” in particular highlight how population concentration and urban mobility play a role in air pollution, reflecting the importance of urban environmental management solutions [75]. Then, “COVID” and “health” mark the influence of the pandemic on air quality dynamics and its public health consequences, while “environmental studies” and “sustainable development” indicate how air quality monitoring is integrated into broader initiatives to maintain ecological balance and health man. By exploring the connections between these themes, researchers can develop more informed and effective strategies for better air quality monitoring, which not only meet technical challenges but also take into account health and environmental aspects. These concept maps are an important tool in identifying unexplored areas of research and potential for innovation, which could ultimately lead to significant changes in the way we understand and address air pollution problems.

3.4. Discussion on limitations

The discussion section delves deeper into the limitations of this study, aiming to offer a thorough understanding of the constraints and possible biases inherent in the methodology. While selecting keywords was meticulously done, it is essential to acknowledge that this approach might introduce bias. The analysis conducted in this study brings to light a critical revelation among various factors influencing air quality. AI and middleware’s role in air quality management is multifaceted and profound, from predictive analytics to real-time monitoring and control strategies. It is important to emphasize that this research highlights the major impact AI will have on air quality monitoring. AI emerged as an important theme in the research, with 1,159 occurrences and 41% relevance in the data set. This underscores the important role AI technology plays in understanding, monitoring and potentially predicting air quality. AI-based approaches, including machine learning algorithms, have revolutionized air quality management by enabling more accurate and real-time data analysis.

AI models can predict the concentration of pollutants like PM_{2.5}, nitrogen oxides, and sulfur dioxide, allowing cities to implement preemptive measures to curb air quality deterioration. AI enhances real-time monitoring of air quality. Advanced sensors, integrated with AI algorithms, provide real-time data on pollutant levels. This constant data stream is crucial for immediate responses to air quality crises. Moreover, AI contributes to air quality research by enabling the analysis of large and complex environmental datasets. This capability facilitates the understanding of air pollution dynamics and the interaction between various pollutants and meteorological factors. Such insights are crucial in developing more effective air quality management strategies.

While discussing the impact of AI on air quality, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations in current research methodologies. The reliance on predefined keywords and subjective assessments in literature reviews, as well as potential biases in data used for AI models, can influence the conclusions drawn. However, the consistent and significant findings across multiple studies reinforce the argument that AI role in improving air quality is substantial and cannot be overlooked. AI is a new breakthrough in managing air quality, with its ability to predict, monitor, and control air pollution changing the way we understand and overcome the challenges of this environment. By continuing to perfect the AI system and overcome the bias methodology, the potential for significant global air quality improvement is increasingly achieved.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study conducted a SLR on air quality articles to identify research gaps and future directions. Analyzing 48 articles published from 2019 to 2023 using Leximancer, the study identified five main themes: air quality, AI, middleware, pollution, and smart environments. The theme of air quality

dominated the dataset with 2,797 occurrences, emphasizing its central role in the research analyzed. Themes AI appeared 1,159 times and was highlighted as crucial for understanding and predicting air quality, while middleware, with 703 occurrences, underscored the importance of technical infrastructure in processing air quality data. Population activity, represented by 525 occurrences, indicated a significant relationship between human activities, air quality, and smart environments, with 521 occurrences showcasing the importance of innovative technologies in addressing air quality challenges. The findings stress the urgency of addressing air quality issues through collaborative and innovative solutions. They emphasize the need for developing sophisticated AI models for better predictions, optimizing middleware to ensure efficient data flow, and increasing public awareness about the impact of air quality on health and the environment. This research highlights the broad and varied implications of air quality, necessitating a multidisciplinary approach that combines expertise from data science, technology, and environmental science. Such an approach promises innovative solutions by integrating diverse perspectives and expertise. Future research should focus on developing AI models to improve the accuracy and timeliness of air quality predictions, exploring middleware optimization to ensure efficient data flow between various platforms in air quality management systems, and investigating the integration of climate change and air pollution to understand their mutual impacts and develop mitigation strategies. Additionally, research should explore policy implications of integrating technological advances with environmental science and evaluate the effectiveness of multidisciplinary approaches in shaping sustainable air quality management policies. Long-term strategies at both global and local levels, with a focus on international cooperation in air quality research and policy, are essential. By detailing and exploring these aspects, future research is expected to make a significant contribution to the understanding and management of air quality globally.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We want to thank the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology for supporting and funding this research through the Applied Research Program with reference number 108/E5/PG.02.00.PL/2024. With their help, this research came to fruition. We also thank the Satya Wacana Christian University, University of Raharja and University of Technology Malaysia for invaluable assistance in completing this study. All contributions and support provided by these parties have been significant for the progress of this research.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Deng *et al.*, "Disease specific air quality health index (AQHI) for spatiotemporal health risk assessment of multi-air pollutants," *Environmental Research*, vol. 231, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2023.115943.
- [2] M. Ramon *et al.*, "Assessment of four urban forest as environmental indicator of air quality: a study in a Brazilian megacity," *Urban Ecosystems*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 197–207, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11252-022-01296-7.
- [3] F. Carozzi and S. Roth, "Dirty density: Air quality and the density of American cities," *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, vol. 118, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jeem.2022.102767.
- [4] M. Méndez, M. G. Merayo, and M. Núñez, "Machine learning algorithms to forecast air quality: a survey," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 56, no. 9, pp. 10031–10066, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10462-023-10424-4.
- [5] Y. Li and R. Li, "A hybrid model for daily air quality index prediction and its performance in the face of impact effect of COVID-19 lockdown," *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, vol. 176, pp. 673–684, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.psep.2023.06.021.
- [6] S. Feng *et al.*, "Long-term improvement of air quality associated with lung function benefits in Chinese young adults: A quasi-experiment cohort study," *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 851, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158150.
- [7] A. Isaza, M. Kay, J. P. Evans, A. Prasad, and S. Bremner, "Air quality impacts on rooftop photovoltaic energy production during the 2019-2020 Australian bushfires season," *Solar Energy*, vol. 257, pp. 240–248, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.solener.2023.04.014.
- [8] D. Jonas, E. Maria, Sutarto, I. R. Widiyasa, U. Rahardja, and T. Wellem, "Design of a TAM framework with emotional variables in the acceptance of health-based IoT in Indonesia," *ADI Journal on Recent Innovation (AJRI)*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 146–154, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.34306/ajri.v5i2.1005.
- [9] R. Kashyap, J. Kuttippurath, and V. K. Patel, "Improved air quality leads to enhanced vegetation growth during the COVID-19 lockdown in India," *Applied Geography*, vol. 151, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.apgeog.2022.102869.
- [10] K. V. Abhijith, P. Kumar, H. Omidvarborna, A. P. M. Emygdio, B. McCallan, and D. C. -Lomax, "Improving air pollution awareness of the general public through citizen science approach," *Sustainable Horizons*, vol. 10, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.horiz.2023.100086.
- [11] H. A. Fakher, Z. Ahmed, A. O. Acheampong, and S. P. Nathaniel, "Renewable energy, nonrenewable energy, and environmental quality nexus: An investigation of the N-shaped environmental Kuznets curve based on six environmental indicators," *Energy*, vol. 263, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2022.125660.
- [12] C. Lukita, "Predictive and analytics using data mining and machine learning for customer churn prediction," *Journal of Applied Data Sciences*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 454–465, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.47738/jads.v4i4.131.
- [13] Y. Feng, M. Ning, W. Xue, M. Cheng, and Y. Lei, "Developing China's roadmap for air quality improvement: A review on technology development and future prospects," *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, vol. 123, pp. 510–521, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jes.2022.10.028.

- [14] T. Kangas, S. Gadeyne, W. Lefebvre, C. Vanpoucke, and L. R. -Loureiro, "Are air quality perception and PM2.5 exposure differently associated with cardiovascular and respiratory disease mortality in Brussels? Findings from a census-based study," *Environmental Research*, vol. 219, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2022.115180.
- [15] U. Rahardja *et al.*, "Evaluating the mediating mechanism of perceived trust and risk toward cryptocurrency: an empirical research," *SAGE Open*, vol. 13, no. 4, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1177/21582440231217854.
- [16] S. Sonawani and K. Patil, "Predicting air quality in smart city using novel transfer learning based framework," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 1014–1021, 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v32.i2.pp1014-1021.
- [17] A. F. Daru, K. D. Hartomo, and H. D. Purnomo, "IPv6 flood attack detection based on epsilon greedy optimized Q learning in single board computer," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 5782–5791, 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v13i5.pp5782-5791.
- [18] J. Y. Lee and N. Aghamohammadi, "Restaurant managers knowledge and intention to improve building ventilation and indoor air quality using control measures in a middle-income country," *Building and Environment*, vol. 244, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110775.
- [19] M. Eriyadi, D. Notosudjono, H. Setiana, and M. A. A. A. Yakin, "Low-cost mobile air quality monitoring based on internet of things for factory area," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 545–554, 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v32.i1.pp545-554.
- [20] S. H. L. Yim and T. Huang, "Analysis of the air quality in upper atmospheric boundary layer in a high-density city in Asia using 3-year vertical profiles measured by the 3-dimensional real-time atmospheric monitoring system (3DREAMS)," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 857, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159137.
- [21] B. Kitchenham, O. P. Brereton, D. Budgen, M. Turner, J. Bailey, and S. Linkman, "Systematic literature reviews in software engineering-A systematic literature review," *Information and Software Technology*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 7–15, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.infsof.2008.09.009.
- [22] F. Alzami, Z. A. Hasibuan, S. A. Wulandari, F. O. Saputra, J. Jumanto, and P. N. Andono, "Component of traffic management system for developing countries: a review," *2022 International Seminar on Application for Technology of Information and Communication: Technology 4.0 for Smart Ecosystem: A New Way of Doing Digital Business, iSemantic 2022*, pp. 436–439, 2022, doi: 10.1109/iSemantic55962.2022.9920460.
- [23] Z. Wei and H. Lihua, "Effects of tourism and eco-innovation on environmental quality in selected ASEAN countries," *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, vol. 30, no. 15, pp. 42889–42903, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11356-021-17541-z.
- [24] Z. Zhang, S. Zhang, C. Chen, and J. Yuan, "A systematic survey of air quality prediction based on deep learning," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 93, pp. 128–141, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2024.03.031.
- [25] A. B. Handoko, V. C. Putra, I. Setyawan, D. Utomo, J. Lee, and I. K. Timotius, "Evaluation of YOLO-X and MobileNetV2 as face mask detection algorithms," *2022 IEEE Industrial Electronics and Applications Conference, IEACon 2022*, pp. 105–110, 2022, doi: 10.1109/IEACon55029.2022.9951831.
- [26] N. Jiang, C. Ao, L. Xu, Y. Wei, and Y. Long, "Will information interventions affect public preferences and willingness to pay for air quality improvement? An empirical study based on deliberative choice experiment," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 868, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161436.
- [27] D. Fu *et al.*, "Why did air quality experience little improvement during the COVID-19 lockdown in megacities, northeast China?," *Environmental Research*, vol. 221, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2023.115282.
- [28] Y. Kuang and B. Lin, "Unwatched pollution reduction: The effect of natural gas utilization on air quality," *Energy*, vol. 273, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2023.127247.
- [29] S. Wang *et al.*, "Unpacking the inter- and intra-urban differences of the association between health and exposure to heat and air quality in Australia using global and local machine learning models," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 871, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.162005.
- [30] P. Zhang *et al.*, "Understanding archetypal spatial gradient patterns in urban economic, population and air quality nexus: New insights from a geographic-process perspective," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 95, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2023.104596.
- [31] A. C. O'Regan and M. M. Nyhan, "Towards sustainable and net-zero cities: A review of environmental modelling and monitoring tools for optimizing emissions reduction strategies for improved air quality in urban areas," *Environmental Research*, vol. 231, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2023.116242.
- [32] G. Arbilla, G. Dantas, and C. M. D. Silva, "Tijuca forest contribution to the improvement of air quality and wellbeing of citizens in the city of Rio de Janeiro, Brazil," *Chemosphere*, vol. 334, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.139017.
- [33] S. Hama, P. Kumar, A. Tiwari, Y. Wang, and P. S. Linden, "The underpinning factors affecting the classroom air quality, thermal comfort and ventilation in 30 classrooms of primary schools in London," *Environmental Research*, vol. 236, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envres.2023.116863.
- [34] M. A. Storey, O. F. Price, and P. F. -Hughes, "The influence of regional wind patterns on air quality during forest fires near Sydney, Australia," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 905, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.167335.
- [35] G. Kuiper *et al.*, "The influence of LEED enhanced indoor air quality credit achievement on COVID-related school closures," *Building and Environment*, vol. 243, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110721.
- [36] D. Li *et al.*, "The influence of anthropogenic emissions on air quality in Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei of China around 2050 under the future climate scenario," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 388, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.135927.
- [37] S. Munir *et al.*, "The impact of smart traffic interventions on roadside air quality employing machine learning approaches," *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment*, vol. 110, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.trd.2022.103408.
- [38] N. Pang, B. Jiang, and Y. Zheng, "The impact of fireworks burning on air quality and their health effects in China during spring festivals of 2015–2022," *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, vol. 14, no. 11, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.apr.2023.101888.
- [39] Z. Yang, Y. Yuan, and Y. Tan, "The impact and nonlinear relationship of low-carbon city construction on air quality: Evidence from a quasi-natural experiment in China," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 422, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138588.
- [40] Y. Jiang, X. Liang, S. Zhang, Z. Hu, A. Hove, and Y. Wu, "The future air quality impact of electric vehicle promotion and coordinated charging in the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region," *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 332, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2023.121928.
- [41] G. Cao, L. A. Zhou, C. Liu, and J. Zhou, "The effects of the entries by bike-sharing platforms on urban air quality," *China Economic Quarterly International*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 213–224, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.ceqi.2023.09.003.
- [42] S. P. -Mangut *et al.*, "Wearable system for outdoor air quality monitoring in a WSN with cloud computing: Design, validation and deployment," *Chemosphere*, vol. 307, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.135948.
- [43] A. Majdi, A. J. Alrubaie, A. H. Al-Wardy, J. Baili, and H. Panchal, "A novel method for indoor air quality control of smart homes using a machine learning model," *Advances in Engineering Software*, vol. 173, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.advengsoft.2022.103253.

- [44] Z. Li, H. Zhang, Y. H. Juan, Y. T. Lee, C. Y. Wen, and A. S. Yang, "Effects of urban tree planting on thermal comfort and air quality in the street canyon in a subtropical climate," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 91, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2022.104334.
- [45] J. Pei, M. Qu, L. Sun, X. Wang, and Y. Yin, "The relationship between indoor air quality (IAQ) and perceived air quality (PAQ)-a review and case analysis of Chinese residential environment," *Energy and Built Environment*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 230–243, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.enbenv.2022.09.005.
- [46] D. Meena, M. Kumar, S. Dhya, N. R. Koli, Y. Tak, and A. K. Meena, "Assessment of correlation and path coefficient analysis for yield and its attributing traits in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) genotypes," *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 7, pp. 3845–3851, 2020, doi: 10.20546/ijcmas.2020.907.450.
- [47] I. Helm, N. Koch, and A. Rohlf, "The effects of cash for clunkers on local air quality," *Journal of Urban Economics*, vol. 138, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jue.2023.103576.
- [48] A. Choi, P. Kim, and A. Park, "The effects of air quality on housing prices: Evidence from the Aliso Canyon gas leak," *Journal of Housing Economics*, vol. 62, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jhe.2023.101966.
- [49] J. Wang *et al.*, "The diminishing effects of winter heating on air quality in northern China," *Journal of Environmental Management*, vol. 325, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116536.
- [50] Y. Rao, C. Wu, and Q. He, "The antagonistic effect of urban growth pattern and shrinking cities on air quality: Based on the empirical analysis of 174 cities in China," *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 97, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2023.104752.
- [51] S. A. Horn and P. K. Dasgupta, "The air quality index (AQI) in historical and analytical perspective a tutorial review," *Talanta*, vol. 267, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.talanta.2023.125260.
- [52] K. Mahmud *et al.*, "Temporal assessment of air quality in major cities in Nigeria using satellite data," *Atmospheric Environment: X*, vol. 20, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.aeaoa.2023.100227.
- [53] V. S. Gamboa, É. J. Kinast, and M. Pires, "System for performance evaluation and calibration of low-cost gas sensors applied to air quality monitoring," *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, vol. 14, no. 2, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.apr.2022.101645.
- [54] X. Wang, M. Wang, X. Liu, Y. Mao, Y. Chen, and S. Dai, "Surveillance-image-based outdoor air quality monitoring," *Environmental Science and Ecotechnology*, vol. 18, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.ese.2023.100319.
- [55] K. Elbaz, I. Hoteit, W. M. Shaban, and S. L. Shen, "Spatiotemporal air quality forecasting and health risk assessment over smart city of NEOM," *Chemosphere*, vol. 313, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.137636.
- [56] Q. Liu, H. Li, W. long Shang, and K. Wang, "Spatio-temporal distribution of Chinese cities' air quality and the impact of high-speed rail," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 170, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2022.112970.
- [57] M. Pathak, V. K. Patel, and J. Kuttippurath, "Spatial heterogeneity in global atmospheric CO during the COVID-19 lockdown: Implications for global and regional air quality policies," *Environmental Pollution*, vol. 335, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.envpol.2023.122269.
- [58] B. Rios, Y. D. -Esteban, and G. B. Raga, "Smoke emissions from biomass burning in Central Mexico and their impact on air quality in Mexico City: May 2019 case study," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 904, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.166912.
- [59] A. Zivelonghi and A. Giuseppi, "Smart healthy schools: an IoT-enabled concept for multi-room dynamic air quality control," *Internet of Things and Cyber-Physical Systems*, vol. 4, pp. 24–31, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.iotcps.2023.05.005.
- [60] M. Pourkiaei and A. C. Romain, "Scoping review of indoor air quality indexes: Characterization and applications," *Journal of Building Engineering*, vol. 75, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jobe.2023.106703.
- [61] A. Beloconi and P. Vounatsou, "Revised EU and WHO air quality thresholds: where does Europe stand?," *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 314, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2023.120110.
- [62] S. Tariq, F. Qayyum, Z. U. -Haq, and U. Mehmood, "Remote sensing of nighttime air quality over the megacity of Lahore, Pakistan," *Urban Climate*, vol. 49, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.uclim.2023.101498.
- [63] J. Xie *et al.*, "Quantitative evaluation of impacts of the steadiness and duration of urban surface wind patterns on air quality," *Science of the Total Environment*, vol. 850, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.157957.
- [64] Z. Wan, Z. Cai, R. Zhao, Q. Zhang, J. Chen, and Z. Wang, "Quantifying the air quality impact of ship emissions in China's Bohai Bay," *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, vol. 193, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.115169.
- [65] Y. Liu, H. Su, J. Gu, Z. Tian, and K. Li, "Quantifying multiple effects of industrial patterns on air quality: Evidence from 284 prefecture-level cities in China," *Ecological Indicators*, vol. 145, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.109722.
- [66] K. Mehmood *et al.*, "Predicting the quality of air with machine learning approaches: Current research priorities and future perspectives," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 379, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134656.
- [67] A. Rowley and O. Karakuş, "Predicting air quality via multimodal AI and satellite imagery," *Remote Sensing of Environment*, vol. 293, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2023.113609.
- [68] K. Yogeswaran, L. Azmi, S. Bhasu, H. N. Isa, and M. A. Aziz, "Physical parameters influence the microbial quality of indoor air in research laboratories: A report from Malaysia," *Kuwait Journal of Science*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 665–673, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.kjs.2023.04.009.
- [69] A. T. Cobbold, M. A. Crane, L. D. Knibbs, I. C. Hanigan, S. P. Greaves, and C. E. Rissel, "Perceptions of air quality and concern for health in relation to long-term air pollution exposure, bushfires, and COVID-19 lockdown: A before-and-after study," *Journal of Climate Change and Health*, vol. 6, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.joclim.2022.100137.
- [70] L. L. Lemon and J. Hayes, "Enhancing trustworthiness of qualitative findings: Using leximancer for qualitative data analysis triangulation," *Qualitative Report*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 604–614, 2020, doi: 10.46743/2160-3715/2020.4222.
- [71] A. E. Smith, "Automatic extraction of semantic networks from text using leximancer," in *Proceedings of the 2003 Human Language Technology Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics-Demonstrations, HLT-NAACL 2003*, 2003, pp. 23–24. doi: 10.3115/1073427.1073439.
- [72] Y. Li, J. E. Guo, S. Sun, J. Li, S. Wang, and C. Zhang, "Air quality forecasting with artificial intelligence techniques: A scientometric and content analysis," *Environmental Modelling and Software*, vol. 149, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.envsoft.2022.105329.
- [73] Y. Wu, T. Liu, S. H. Ling, J. Szymanski, W. Zhang, and S. W. Su, "Air quality monitoring for vulnerable groups in residential environments using a multiple hazard gas detector," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 2, 2019, doi: 10.3390/s19020362.
- [74] R. Bdiwi, C. D. Runz, S. Faiz, and A. A. Cherif, "Towards a new ubiquitous learning environment based on blockchain technology," in *Proceedings-IEEE 17th International Conference on Advanced Learning Technologies, ICALT 2017*, 2017, pp. 101–102. doi: 10.1109/ICALT.2017.37.
- [75] A. Souri, A. Hussien, M. Hoseyninezhad, and M. Norouzi, "A systematic review of IoT communication strategies for an efficient smart environment," *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, vol. 33, no. 3, 2022, doi: 10.1002/ett.3736.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Danny Manongga Doctor of Philosophy degree from the University of East Anglia, England in 1996. He also obtained an M.Sc. in IT Queen Mary College, London in 1989. Currently he serves as a professor in the Department of Computer Science at Satya Wacana Christian University, Salatiga, Indonesia. His research includes information systems, knowledge management and artificial intelligence. He has published more than 100 papers in international journals and conferences. He can be contacted at email: danny.manongga@uksw.edu.

Untung Rahardja is bachelor graduate from the University of California Berkeley in America, followed by a Masters Study Program in Information Technology at the University of Indonesia. Currently, he is again expanding his wings in the field of management science, having successfully completed a Masters in Management at Persada Indonesia University YAI and completed a doctoral program in management science at Gajah Mada University and Persada Indonesia University YAI. The year 2022 be a historic moment when he achieves the title of Professor. Have scientific work published in the arena of national and international reputation. Among them are 10+ book creations published in Gramedia and Andi Offset, 250+ scientific journals indexed by Google Scholar, 40+ journals indexed by Scopus. He can be contacted at email: rahardjauntung@graduate.utm.my.

Irwan Sembiring Master of Computer Science degree from Gadjah Mada University, Jogjakarta, Indonesia in 2016. He also received doctor of Computer Science from Gadjah Mada University in 2004. Currently he is Lecturer and Researcher, Digital Forensic Specialist Satya Wacana Christian University in 2006 and as IT Consultant, IT Manager, MIS in Indonesia. His research includes digital forensics, information systems, and artificial intelligence. He has published more than 100 papers in international journals and conferences. He can be contacted at email: irwan@uksw.edu.

Qurotul Aini is a lecturer in the field of information systems. Obtained a master's degree from University of Raharja in 2016. She has 176 research studies in gamification, blockchain, artificial intelligence, internet, and e-commerce, published worldwide with reputations from Sinta to Scopus. She can be contacted at email: aini@raharja.info.

Po Abas Sunarya Master of State Administration at the STIA Menarasiswa Campus. He spread his wings in the field of management science, having successfully completed his Master of Management education at Pasundan University (UNPAS) Bandung. This should be used as a benchmark for persistence in completing the Public Administration Management Science Doctoral Program to pursue the tridharma of education and teaching, research, community service while busy pursuing further higher education. His research includes digital forensics, information systems, and artificial intelligence. He has published more than 100 papers in international journals and conferences. He can be contacted at email: abas@raharja.info.